

WATER AVAILABILITY BASED CROP SPECIFIC

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Abstract—Machine learning is a key element of the growing field of data science. Algorithms are trained to generate classifications or predictions using statistical techniques, revealing important insights in data mining operations. Terrestrial ecology depends heavily on water resources, and it is anticipated that climate change would significantly shift where this valuable resource is found. To meet the needs, agriculture needs to improve in a country like India where the population is growing and there is a constant demand for food. Crop Yield Prediction is still a difficult task in this field. However, farming done in an unscientific manner owing to lack of awareness leading to lower productivity and over exploitation of the scarce water resources. This research provides a government to citizen app to developed for water availability-based crop-specific farming advisory integrating soil health card data, rainfall forecasting data and information about local surface and ground water resources. This research will advise the farmers to follow a particular cropping pattern based upon time of the year. Hence by utilizing our system farmers can cultivate a new variety of crop, may increase in profit margin. In previous paper they have an accuracy > 80 %. So, this project is researching in it and try to improvise the accuracy > 99 %

Keywords—*Random Forest, Crop Prediction, Machine Learning, Agriculture*

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is one of the most significant professions conducted in India. It is the most inclusive economic sector and has a major significant part in the nation's overall development. More than 60 % of the country's land is used for agriculture. In order to meet the requirements of 1.3 billion people. Modern agricultural technology is crucial. This is going to lead our nation's farmers to financial success. Agriculture practices are being modernized today for the benefit of the farmers. Crop yield or output is largely influenced by weather, environmental changes, rainfall (which can be unpredictable at times), water management, and the use of pesticides. Consequently, farmers are unable to achieving crop yield expectations. Currently, a number of academics are using data mining, machine learning, and deep learning techniques to increase crop productivity and quality. Prior crop and yield predictions were made based on the knowledge of farmers in a certain area. They don't know

about the crop cultivating in different places and those who are not in the field of farming don't know about the crop that they want to cultivate in a particular place if they cultivate wrong crop it will lead to reduces yield, causes soil pollution and harms the top layer of the soil. We developed the system using machine learning with the goal of improving the farmer's situation while taking all these issues into consideration. Machine learning (ML) is revolutionizing the agricultural industry. Artificial intelligence, which includes machine learning, big data, and high-performance computing, has evolved to open up new possibilities for data-intensive science in the multidisciplinary field of agrotechnology. Machine learning, for instance, is not a magic trick or a mystery trick in the field of agriculture; rather, it is a collection of well-defined models that gather particular data and use particular methods to produce predicted results. Numerous studies are being conducted in an effort to develop a reliable and effective model for crop prediction. One such method used in these research projects is ensemble. This study suggests a system that uses the voting method to create an effective and accurate model among the numerous machine learning techniques currently being employed in this industry. The system's recommendations for the best crop for a specific plot of land based on soil composition and climatic variables such as rainfall, temperature, humidity, nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus and PH. The required input is obtained from the farmers or sensors that measure things like temperature, humidity, rainfall, and ph. To find patterns in the data and then process it in accordance with the input requirements, this entire set of input data is applied to the machine-learning predictive algorithm Random Forest. The crop is suggested to the farmer by the system.

II. SCOPE OF THE PROJECT

The demand for agriculture to expand is high as the population all over the world is rising rapidly, so the demand for food is also high. To satisfy this need cultivation of more food crops is necessary, but this process cannot be done everywhere, since different crops need certain requirements for them to be cultivated. The soil of the land for cultivation

can be tested to find which crop could be grown at that place, but this test would sometimes take months to give the result by which the season would've changed and the cultivation should wait to be started again. This problem could be dealt with, with this application as the main concept of this is to quickly find the crop that could be cultivated with the features such as nitrogen, potassium, and phosphate of the location as input. For this application to work to its full extent the following architecture should be framed properly:

1. Application
2. API wiring
3. Random Forest

The application's framework should be developed with the thought that the users of this would mostly be farmers and people who are new to the agriculture field, so the front-end of this application should be kept so easy to cruise through and user-friendly. The application should ask for the location of the user at the starting point to start it quickly, then the next screen would contain the text fields where the user has to input the values of the soil's Nitrogen, Potassium and Phosphate and then when the find button is clicked the model would work on the inputs and predict the crop that can be cultivated. The application should be wired with API for fetching the temperature, humidity and groundwater level, and then storing the values in the text field. The fetching of these values could be performed with a get function and then the API would fetch the values from the destination and store them in the text fields. The model is created with the Random Forest algorithm, this algorithm takes the input and starts creating multiple numbers of Decision trees. Each decision tree predicts an output, and then the overall is taken into consideration to find which is predicted numerous times and then that value is given as the output. The advantage of this algorithm is the usage of numerous decision trees, which will make the accuracy of the prediction high. Therefore this algorithm integrating with all the frameworks would bring the application to life and help the users get benefitted from it.

literature survey

In agriculture field, variety of work that has been done with the use of machine learning, it is thought of as a fresh field in this industry. Researchers from all around the world have developed and assessed a variety of philosophies in the fields of agriculture and allied sciences. Vishnu Vardhan, CH Dr. K. Venkataramana Chowdary created the ID3 algorithm, which runs on the PHP framework and uses CSV datasets to obtain an increased and excellent tomato crop production. The various characteristics employed in this study include temperature, area, humidity, and tomato crop production. Data mining techniques are used by R. Sujatha and P. Isakki to make predictions. This model utilised a variety of inputs, including crop name, land area, soil type, pH value, seed type, and water. It also predicted plant growth and illnesses, enabling users to select the best crop based on climatic information and necessary inputs. The SVM was proposed by N. Gandhi, L. J. Armstrong, O. Petkar, and A. K. Tripathy for the prediction of rice crop yield. The dataset employed in this method includes a variety of factors, including location, temperature, precipitation, and manufacturing. The implemented classifier uses sequential minimal optimization for this dataset. To create the set of rules on the existing dataset, they prepared the dataset using the Weka tool. SVM algorithm results were developed in Python. S. Veenadhari, B.

Misra, and C. Singh have created an interactive website called Crop Advisor that uses the c4.5 algorithm to determine how the climate affects crop productivity. The development of decision trees and rules is dependent on the c4.5 algorithm. It illustrates how many climate factors influence crop development. Environmental characteristics from the relevant years, such as rainfall and temperature, were studied. The zones under the selected crop determined the options. The selection tree that Jun Wu, Anastasiya Olesnikova, Chi-Hwa Song, and Won Don Lee suggested is suitable for classifying all types of farming records. A decision tree classifier was put out to classify agricultural data. It makes use of fresh information and can deal with all records. Horse-colic and soyabean datasets are checked using the 10-fold cross validation approach. In their paper, Kiran Mai, C., Murali Krishna, I.V, and A. Venugopal Reddy described how data mining is combined with other farming data, such as meteorological data, usage of pesticides, and are useful for easing out of use of pesticides. Agriculture related current events were represented, together with adjacent International Journal of Engineering Research Technology (IJERT) features. In their work, Verheyen, K., Adrianens, M. Hermy, and S. Deckers discussed statistical mining techniques, which are frequently used to assess soil characteristics. As kmeans is combined with GPS based technology to section soils. 10 In order to increase the farmer's profit and the standard of the agricultural industry, Ashwani Kumar Kushwaha outlines crop yield prediction methods and suggests a suitable crop. Using the Hadoop platform and an agricultural algorithm, this research predicts crop yield using massive volumes of data, also known as big data (soil and meteorological data). Therefore, based on repository data, one may forecast if a crop is suitable for a given condition and enhance crop quality. Girish L describes how to anticipate crop productivity and rainfall using machine learning. In this research, many machine learning techniques for crop yield and rainfall prediction are discussed, along with the effectiveness of various machine learning algorithms such as linear regression, SVM, KNN method, and decision tree. In this paper, many artificial intelligence methods, including big data analysis for precision agriculture and machine learning algorithms, are covered. In their explanations, they use KNN, Ensemble-based Models, Neural Networks, etc. to discuss crop recommender systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

Random Forest is a classifier that contains a number of decision trees on various subsets of the given dataset and takes the average to improve the predictive accuracy of that dataset. It can be used for both Classification and Regression problems in ML. It is based on the concept of ensemble learning, which is a process of combining multiple classifiers to solve a complex problem and to improve the performance of the model. The multiple classifiers in the Random Forest are the decision trees. It takes less training time as compared to other algorithms. It predicts output with high accuracy, even for the large dataset it runs efficiently. It can also maintain accuracy when a large proportion of data is missing. The greater number of trees in the forest leads to higher accuracy and prevents the problem of overfitting. Decision Tree has a three-layer Neural Network. The Neural Network has two trainable layers:

1. The decision tree nodes The Decision tree nodes has two nodes, the root and the intermediate. The root node is the

node that starts the graph. In a normal decision tree, it evaluates the variable that best splits the data. The Intermediate nodes These are nodes where variables are evaluated but which are not the final nodes where predictions are made.

2. The leaf nodes. The Leaf nodes are the final nodes of the tree, where the predictions of a category or a numerical value are made

The Working process can be explained in the below

Step-1: Select random K data points from the training set.

Step-2: Build the decision trees associated with the selected data points (Subsets).

Step-3: Choose the number N for decision trees that you want to build.

Step-4: Repeat Step 1 ,2.

Step-5: For new data points, find the predictions of each decision tree, and assign the new data points to the category that wins the majority votes.

IV. CONCLUSION

The Agriculture sector is the backbone of the country, it is so important for the survival of human beings as it is the source of the food we consume. More and more developments in this sector are needed to get the best out of it while using the resources to their extent with minimum effort. One of the issues that are faced in this sector is trying to find the correct type of crop for cultivating in a particular land, if this is not figured properly and if the cultivated crop is not suitable for the land then the crop would not produce any yield and the resources spent on it would all be for waste. Sometimes when a farmer tries to cultivate in a new land or a person who is new to this field will find it difficult to figure out which crop is

suitable for cultivation, for these people a solution is needed to help them in the sector. The model provides a solution for this issue that is faced. It is able to predict which crop is suitable for the chosen land. The user enters the information about the land like nitrogen, potassium, phosphate and etc, while the API in the model fetches the information about the environmental factors of the location that is chosen. The model takes the information as input and it is trained to process that information and provide the crop that could be cultivated in the location, and the result is also provided with accuracy. So this model could be put to great use and will help in the development of the agriculture sector.

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